

GRAVURE, THE PRINTERS DELIGHT: IT'S ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

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Abstract

Gravure is a major printing process. About fifteen (15%) of all printing in the United State is done by gravure. Certainly it must have doubled. As at 1986, the gravure industry has enjoyed a steady growth rate and with recent technical advances, it will continue to gain a larger share of the printing market worldwide.

Introduction

Gravure Cylinders

Most commercial printing processes use printing cylinders rather than plates. This process is also called rotogravure. Most gravure cylinders are made by (Clechromechemical engraving)

There are several advantages and disadvantages in gravure reproduction methods. They are all important considering production of printed products.

Because the gravure is normally printed on a rotary press, it is commonly referred to as Roto gravure.

Several important characteristics make gravure an ideal process for jobs requiring high quality and extremely long press runs.

Gravure is the simplest of all printing systems, with the faster press start-up and the most direct press controls.

This process has the capacity to produce images on a great variety of materials, for example gravure is used in Vinyl Fabrics² Printed products in this

category include supported vinyl fabrics for wall covers, auto and furniture upholstery to mention a few.

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

Due to the fact that gravure has easy press control, this results in very little substrates waste. As a matter of fact, gravure has less than half the paper spoilage rate of lithography³.

The process has the ability for extremely fast speed. The speed of gravure is very exceptional. The largest gravure presets can operate as rapidly as 750 feet per minute Rotogravure presses can run at speeds of more than 3,000 feet (900 meters) per minutes⁴.

Another important thing to know about this process is that it allows the printing of high quality images on low grade papers. This high quality reproduction results on inexpensive printing substrates such as Newsprint paper.

The cylinder is especially hardy. It has the longest image life of the image carriers. Several million impressions from the same cylinders are common. Some printers report the press runs as long as 20 million copies without the cylinder wearing out.⁵

Gravure process has the reputation of delivering excellent color and ink density even on low quality printing papers. It produces color that looks almost like continuous tone printing. This is similar to color photographic prints. The process is also known for fast drying ink which solves the problem of smearing, set-off common to letterpress and lithography.

Make ready problems are fewer on a rotogravure press. In theory, all the printing cylinders for a particular job are uniform in circumference, and all cells have been made to hold their prescribed ink volumes. Therefore, the images are fixed with regard to their color density (ink film thickness) and positioning of the image (registration) on the substrate. It almost always requires less make ready time to set up a modern rotogravure press than an equivalent flexo or web-offset

press.

Having considered the significant advantages of this process, it is important to mention the short comings of this process.

Rotogravure is a complex printing process. It takes sophisticated and expensive equipment, rigid standards quality control, precise attention to detail and the combined skills of hundreds of different craftsmen.

Another disadvantage of this process is the length of time required to prepare the printing cylinder. Also included is the initial high cost of producing image carriers like wrap around plates and cylinders. The cost of cylinder preparation is so much higher than other processes that some companies refuse jobs less than a million copies.⁶

Furthermore, the process is limited to specific type size and styles. Type smaller than 8 point should not be used unless necessary for readability and the type face cannot contain hairline strokes⁷. The type should be medium to bold type which lacks fine details.

One of the disadvantages of this process also is the inability to make quick and easy image carrier changes. If one part of the total image needs to be changed, the entire image carrier must be re-etched. This takes time and it is quite expensive. More also accurate precision is required to obtain quality results.

As regards the ink problem, one of the significant causes of wasted time and materials in color printing arises because of the somewhat subjective nature of the process. Generally a transparency or reflection prints is presented for reproduction by the customer which cannot be readily exactly copied by the printing process.

The average gravure packaging printers has a rather investment in completed gravure cylinders (tooling), and in most cases it is larger than required of a flexographic printer. Rotogravure printers have a larger investment in their tooling than they do in their printing presses.

The high cost, both in time and skilled labor, to produce a rotogravure cylinder is the major disadvantage of the gravure process. A typical gravure cylinder can cost from 8 to 20 times more than wraparound printing plates. In 1985, the approximate cost of an American made 1250mm (50) wide finished gravure cylinder is US\$2,000.⁸

Another disadvantage of a gravure press concerns the changing of the impression roller for different web widths. Large amounts of impression pressure are needed to force the ink out of the gravure cells onto the material being printed. Smooth substrates (films) require the least amount of impression pressure (900 kg/m, 50 pile), while rough surfaced materials (paperboard need the highest amount (4500 kg/m, 250 pile).⁹ The soft rubber covering on the impression roller will become distorted under these pressure levels, and the amount of distortion is a function of the amount of nipping pressure and the hardness of the rubber covering.

SUMMARY

The Gravure printing process can be considered to be the most complex of all printing processes. i.e Letterpress, Lithography silk screen printing. The Rotogravure produces a greater flexibility in the range of screens available. One can go from a coarse screen of about 128 lines per inch and even tinier. The range of machine bed sizes has been increased, so that new the largest machines will handle cylinders up to 148 inches in length. This become necessary as publication presses have become larger and also because some very large cylinders are being used in other areas of the gravure industry.

CONCLUSION

To really conclude whether the Rotogravure stand the test of time, the need arise to review work done in Europe with the Helio-Klischograph. That the most accessible was the magazine Der Spiegel, which is Newsweek or time type magazine produced weekly on a very short production schedule by the firm of Axel Springer in Hamburg, Germany Reviewing a dozen or so issues of this magazine, it was found that the majority of the pages were produced on the Helio Klischograph that is, both of black and white exhibit the highest and sharpest copy and readability.

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